

THERAPEUTIC SIGNIFICANCE OF KAVALA AND GANDUSHA IN MUKHAROGA**Dr. Akanksha^{1*}, Prof. Dr. Vijayant Bhardwaj²**¹PG Scholar, Dept. of Shalakya Tantra, Rajiv Gandhi Government Post Graduate Ayurvedic College and Hospital, Paprola, Distt. Kangra, Himachal Pradesh.²HOD, Dept. of Shalakya Tantra, Rajiv Gandhi Government Post Graduate Ayurvedic College and Hospital, Paprola, Distt. Kangra, Himachal Pradesh.***Corresponding Author: Dr. Akanksha**

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ABSTRACT

Ayurveda recommends *Kavala* and *Gandusha*, simple daily cleansing procedures described under *Dinacharya*, for maintaining oral hygiene and preventing disease. These therapies benefit both healthy and diseased individuals due to their preventive and therapeutic actions. According to Ayurvedic principles, imbalance in doshas caused by factors such as oral unhygiene, stress, nutritional deficiencies, and allergies leads to numerous oral disorders (*Mukharogas*). *Kavala* and *Gandusha*, part of *Kriyakaalpa* therapies, help restore balance, promote oral health, and support the overall functioning of the seven components of the oral cavity. This paper provides a brief review of these practices, highlighting their benefits and role in managing oral diseases.

KEYWORDS: *Kavala, Gandusha, Mukharogas, Kriyakaalpa.***INTRODUCTION**

The treatment and prevention of oral diseases, the procedures of keeping medicinal liquids in the mouth—*Kavala* and *Gandusha*—have been described in Ayurvedic literature. These procedures are extremely important in dentistry. The main difference between *Kavala* and *Gandusha* lies in their method of holding the liquid in the mouth and the quantity used.

In *Gandusha*, the mouth is completely filled with the medicinal liquid so that no space remains inside.^[1] In *Kavala*, the quantity of liquid is less, so there remains some space in the mouth, and the medicine can be moved or swished around.^[2] These therapies remove conditions such as excessive *Kapha*, dryness of the mouth, foul smell, heaviness, and diseases of the teeth, gums, and tongue. They strengthen the jaw, improve taste perception, and remove stickiness. After proper *Gandusha*, the mouth feels light and fresh. *Gandusha* gradually removes excessive saliva, bad taste, and sliminess and increases clarity of speech. Depending on the medicinal substance used, *Gandusha* may be of various types—cleansing, strengthening, healing, soothing, etc. *Kavala* and *Gandusha* are useful in diseases like mouth ulcers, gingivitis, stomatitis, dryness of the mouth, stickiness, excessive salivation, jaw

stiffness, and diseases caused by vitiated *Kapha* and *Pitta*.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

1. The material of this review is a comprehensive matter, which is collected from seven classical texts covering *Samhita* period to early modern period i.e. *Charaka Samhita* (300 BC), *Sushruta Samhita* (200 BC), *Ashtanga Hridaya* (600 AD), *Sarangdhara Samhita* (1300 AD), *Bhavaprakasa* (1600 AD), *Yogaratanakara* (1700 AD) and *Chakradutta* (1000AD).

2. On the basis of all the above literature a conclusive list of classical *Yogas* which are useful for *Mukharoga* is prepared.

Table no. 1: Kavala and Gandusha in Mukha Roga mentioned in Charaka Samhita.^[3]

Sr. no.	Drug and mode of administration	Indication	Reference
1.	<i>Taila, Mutra, Ghrita, Madhu, Ksheer</i>	As Kavala in Mukha Paka	Ch. Chi. 26/ 204 Pg. no. 754
2.	<i>Khadiradi Taila</i>	All types of <i>Danta, Mukha</i> and <i>Kantha Roga</i>	Ch. Chi. 26/206-214 pg no. 754 755

Table no. 2: Kavala and Gandusha in Mukha Roga mentioned in Sushruta Samhita.^[4]

Sr. no.	Drug and mode of administration	Indication	Reference
1.	After <i>Raktamokshana Shirovirechana, Dhooma, Sweda</i> and <i>Kavala</i>	<i>Kaphaja Osth Roga</i>	Su. Chi. 22/7 pg no 122
2.	After <i>Raktamokshana, Gandusha</i> with <i>Shunthi, Sarshapa, Nagarmotha, Triphala Rasaunta Kwatha Gandusha</i>	<i>Shitada Danta Roga</i>	Su. Chi. 22/11 pg no 122
3.	<i>Pippali Churan</i> with <i>Madhu Kavala</i>	<i>Adhimansa</i>	Su. Chi. 22/25 pg no 123
4.	<i>Chaturvidha Sneha</i> or <i>Trivritghrita</i> and <i>Vataghana Dravya Kwatha- Sukhoshna Kavala</i>	<i>Dantaharsha</i>	Su. Chi. 22/ 34 pg no. 124
5.	<i>Gandusha</i> prepared from <i>Kshirivriksha Kwatha</i> mixed with <i>Madhu, Ghrita,</i> and <i>Sharkara</i>	<i>Dantaveshtha</i>	Su. Chi. 22/15 pg no. 122
6.	<i>Kshirivriksha Kwatha - Gandusha</i>	<i>Saushira</i>	Su. Chi. 22/ 17 pg no 122
7.	<i>Snehana Gandusha</i>	<i>Krimidanta(immovable)</i>	Su. Chi. 22/38-39 pg no 124
8.	<i>Kavala</i> prepared with <i>Pippali, Saunth, Sarshapa, Vetasapatra Churna</i> mixed with luke warm water or <i>Madhura Dravya Ghrita</i> for <i>Kavala</i>	<i>Upkusha</i>	Su. Chi. 22/ 19-21 pg no 123
9.	<i>Gor Sarshapa</i> with <i>Saindhava Lavana-Kavala</i>	<i>Kaphaja Jihwakantaka</i>	Su. Chi. 22/ 46-47 Pg no. 125
10.	After <i>Lekhana, Pratisarana</i> with <i>Kshara</i> and administration of <i>Gandusha</i>	<i>Upjihva</i>	Su. Chi. 22/ 48 Pg no 125
11.	<i>Snehaukta</i> lukewarm <i>Gandusha</i>	<i>Vataja Rohini</i>	Su.Chi. 22/ 60 pg no 126
12.	<i>Draksha, Parushaka Kwatha Kavala</i>	<i>Pittaja Rohini</i>	Su.Chi. 22/ 61 pg no 126
13.	<i>Taila</i> prepared with <i>Shveta, Vidanga, Danti, Saindhava Lavana</i> for <i>Nasya</i> and <i>Kavala</i>	<i>Kaphaja Rohini</i>	Su. Chi. 22/62 pg no. 126
14.	<i>Taila</i> prepared with <i>Vatahara Dravya</i> for <i>Kavala</i>	<i>Vataja Sarvasara (Mukhapaka)</i>	Su. Chi. 22/ 67 pg no 127
15.	<i>Kaphanashaka Gandusha</i>	<i>Kaphaja Sarvasara (Mukhapaka)</i>	Su. Chi. 22/ 73 pg no 128
16.	After <i>Snehana, Shodhana -Nasaya</i> and <i>Kavala</i>	<i>Swarbheda</i>	Su. Utr. 53/9 Pg no 503

Table no. 3: Kavala and Gandusha in Mukha Roga mentioned in Ashtanga Hridya.^[5]

Sr. no.	Drug and mode of administration	Indication	Reference
1.	<i>Kaphanashaka Gandusha</i>	<i>Kaphaja osth roga</i>	A.H.Utr. 22/8 pg. no. 715
2.	<i>Kavala</i> prepared with <i>Musta, Arjunatwaka, Triphala, Priyangu, Rasanjana, Sauntha Kwatha</i>	<i>Shitada</i>	A.H.Utr. 22/28 pg.no. 717
3.	After <i>Chedana, Pratisarana, Kavala</i> with <i>Patola, Neemba, Triphala Kashaya</i>	<i>Adhimansa</i>	A.H.Utr. 22/38 pg. no. 718
4.	<i>Tila</i> and <i>Mulathi Sadhita Dugdha Gandusha</i>	<i>Dantaharsha and Dantavaidharva</i>	A.H.Utr.22/13 pg.no. 716

5.	After Chedana, Lekhana, Pratisarana and then Gandusha with Kshaya of Lodhra, Musta, Triphala, Rasanjana, Shreshtha Takshrya, Patanga, Kinshuka	Saushira	A.H.Utr. 22/35-36 pg no.717
6.	After Swedana, Vistravana Gandusha with Snigdha and Vatanashaka	Krimidanta (immovable)	A.H.Utr.22/19 pg no. 716
7.	Dashmoola Kwatha with Sneha Gandusha	Dantasthirta Karaka	A.H.Utr.22/14 pg no 716
8.	Hingu, Katphala, Kasees, Sarjikshara, Kushtha, Vayavidanga Sadhita Taila or Eranda, Dwivyaghari, Bhukadamba Kwatha Sadhita Taila Gandusha	Dantashoola Nashaka	A.H.Utr.22/22 pg no 716
9.	Kshirivriksha Kwatha Gandusha	Danta Nadi	A.H.Utr.22/41 pg. no. 718
10.	After Shodhana, Nasya and Sheetala Gandusha	Vidharva	A.H.Utr.22/39 pg no. 718
11.	After Pratisarana Kavala with Ghritamanda or Taila	Upkusha	A.H.Utr.22/29 pg no.717
12.	After Rakta Vistravana, Madhuradravya Pratisarana, Gandusha should be administered	Pittaja Jihwakantaka	A.H.Utr.22/43 pg no 718
13.	Bilwadi Panchmoola Kwatha Kavala, Taila Gandusha	Vataja Rohini	A.H.Utr.22/59 Pg. no. 720
14.	After Gharshana with Sita, Madhu, Priyangu. Kavala with Lodhra, Priyangu, Lal Chandana Draksha and Parushaka Kwatha Kavala	Pittaja Rohini	A.H.Utr.18/60 Pg no 720
15.	Apamargaphala, Shveta, Danti, Vayavidanga, Saindhava Sadhita Taila – Nasya and Gandusha	Kaphaja Rohini	A.H.Utr.22/62 Pg no. 720
16.	Kanjiadi Amla Dravya- Gandusha	Talu Shosha	A.H.Utr.22/53 Pg no. 719
17.	Sheetala Kshaya and Madhura Aushadi – Kavala Adusa, Neemba, Patoladi or Tikta Dravya- Kavala	Talu Paka(Apakava) Talu Paka(Pakava)	A.H.Utr.22/51, A.H.Utr.22/52 Pg no.719
18.	Vataghana Dravya Sadhita Taila – Kavala	Vataja Sarvsara(mukhpaka)	A.H.Utr.22/75, pg no 721
19.	Kaphaghana Dravya- Gandusha Katuki, Atvisha, Patha, Nimba,Rasna, Vacha Kwatha-Kavala	Galashundi	A.H.Utr.22/46, A.H.Utr.22/49
20.	Arimedadi Taila Kshudra, Guduchi, Chamelipatra, Daruharidra, Yavasa, Triphala Kshaya Kwatha mixed with Madhu – Kavala	Mukha Roga Nashaka	A.H.Utr.22/95-96 Pg no 723 A.H.Utr.22/97, pg no 724
21.	Patola, Shunthi, Triphala, Indravaruni, Trayanti, Haridra, Daruharidra, Guduchi with Madhu Gandusha	Mukha Roga Nashaka	A.H.Utr.22/104 Pg no. 724

Table no. 4: Kavala and Gandusha in Mukha Roga mentioned in Sharangdhara Samhita.^[6]

Sr. no.	Drug and mode of administration	Indication	Reference
1.	Snehika Gandusha- Tila Kalkaudaka, Ksheer and Sneha	Vataja prakopa	Sh.S.Utr 10/8
2.	Tila, Neelautpala, Ghrita, Sharkara, Ksheer, Madhu in equal amount – Gandusha	Mukha Daha Nashaka	Sh.S.Utr 10/9
3.	Madhu Gandusha	Mukha Vrana, Dahanashaka, Trishnanashaka	Sh.S.Utr 10/10
4.	Ghrita or Ksheer	Vish, Kshar, Agni Mukhadagdha	Sh.S.Utr 10/11
5.	Taila mixed with Saindhava Lavana	Dantachala	Sh.S.Utr 10/12
6.	Kanjika Gandusha	Mukhashosha Kaphaja Roga	Sh.S.Utr 10/13
7.	Triphala Kwatha mixed with Madhu Gandusha	Kapharakta Nashaka	Sh.S.Utr 10/14
8.	Kwatha of Daruharidra, Guduchi, Triphala, Jatipatra, Draksha, Yavasa and mixed with 1/6 th part of Madhu	Tridoshaja Mukhapaka	Sh.S.Utr 10/15

Table no. 5: Kavala and Gandusha in Mukha Roga mentioned in Bhava Prakasha Samhita.^[7]

Sr. no.	Drug and mode of administration	Indication	Reference
1.	After Shodhana, do Swedana then administration of Kavala	Medoja Oshtha Roga	B.P.Madhyama Khand 66/17 pg no 703
2.	After Raktaprasadana Gandusha of Sauntha, Sarshapa, Triphala Kwatha	Shitada	B.P.Madhyama Khand 66/38 pg no 706
3.	After Chedana and Pratisarana, Pippali and Madhu- Kavala	Adhimansa	B.P.Madhyama Khand 66/54 pg no 707
4.	Lakshaadi Taila Kavala	Dantaroga	B.P.Madhyama Khand 66/73-76 pg no 710
5.	Sneha(Taila,Ghritadi), Ghrita prepared with Nishotha or Kavala with Kwatha prepared from Vatanashaka Dravya	Dantaharsha	B.P.Madhyama Khand 66/81 pg no 711
6.	After Raktaprasadana , Lodhraadi Lepa – Use of Kshirivriksha Kwatha Gandusha	Saushira	B.P.Madhyama Khand 66/48 pg no 707
7.	After Swedana do Raktamokshana, Avapeedana Nasya then Vatanashaka Sneha – Gandusha	Krimidanta(immovable)	B.P.Madhyama Khand 66/77 pg no 710
8.	After Raktaprasadana, Kavala of Guduchi, Pippali, Nimba or Katu Dravya Kwatha	Jihwagata Roga	B.P.Madhyama Khand 66/92 pg no 712
9.	After Raktaprasadana, Madhuragana Dravya - Kavala	Pittaja Jihwakantaka	B.P.Madhyama Khand 66/93 pg no 712
10.	After Raktaprasadana, Pratisarana with Sharkara,Madhu, Priyangu. Draksha & Parushaka Kwatha Kavala	Pittaja Rohini	B.P.Madhyama Khand 66/135 pg no 719
10.	Kavala with Taila prepared from Shveta, Vidanga, Danti Kalka mixed with Saindhava Lavana	Kaphaja Rohini	B.P.Madhyama Khand 66/136 pg no 719
11.	Vacha, Ativisha, Patha, Rasana,Katukrohini Kwatha -Kavala	Talu Roga	B.P.Madhyama Khand 66/110 pg no 714
12.	After Pratisarana with Lavana Churna, Kavala with Taila prepared from Vatanashaka Dravya	Vataja Sarvasara(Mukhapaka)	B.P.Madhyama Khand 66/153 pg no 721
13.	Panchavalakala Kwatha, Triphala Kwatha-Gandusha Tila, Neelautapala, Ghrita Sharkara, Ksheer, Madhu-Kavala Taila prepared from Haridra, Nimbapatra, Madhuka, Neelautpala- Kavala	Mukhapaka	B.P.Madhyama Khand 66/158 pg no 721 B.P.Madhyama Khand 66/163 pg no 722, B.P.Madhyama Khand 66/165 pg no 703

Table no. 6: Kavala and Gandusha in Mukha Roga mentioned in Yogaratnakara.^[8]

Sr. no.	Drug and mode of administration	Indication	Reference
1.	Sauntha & Parpata Kwatha for Gandusha	Shitada	Y.R.Dantamoola Chi. 1 pg no.298
2.	Gandusha with Taila mixed with Kwatha prepared from Panchaungali Kantakari	Krimidanta	Y.R.Dantaroga Chi. 4 Pg. no.301
3.	Sneha Kavala	Dantaharsha	Y.R.Dantaharsha Chi. 1 pg. no.301
4.	After Raktamokshana Kavala with Kwatha prepared from Guduchi, Pippali, Nimba, Trikatu	Jihwa Roga	Y.R.Jihwaroga Chi. 1 pg. no.304
5.	After Raktamokshana Gandusha with Madhura Aushadhi	Pittaja Jihwakantaka	Y.R. Jihwaroga Chi. 3 pg no.304
6.	After Raktamokshana Kavala prepared with Vyosha, Kshar, Abhya, Chitrakamoola	Upajihwa	Y.R. Jihwaroga Chi. 4-5 pg no. 304
7.	After Raktamokshana, Pratisarana with Lavana and then use of Gandusha	Sadhya Rohini	Y.R.Rohini Chi. 1 Pg no.305
8.	After Raktamokshana &	Vataja Rohini	Y.R.Rohini Chi. 2

	<i>Pratisarana with Lavana Gandusha of Sukhoshana Sneha</i>		Pg no.305
9.	<i>Kavala prepared from Draksha and Parushaka Kwatha</i>	<i>Pittaja Rohini</i>	Y.R.Rohini Chi. 3 Pg no.305
10.	<i>Kavala with Taila prepared from Shveta, Vidanga, Danti Kalka mixed with Saindhava Lavana</i>	<i>Kaphaja Rohini</i>	Y.R.Rohini Chi. 4 Pg no.305
11.	<i>Kavala with Taila prepared from Vatanashaka Aushadi</i>	<i>Vataja Sarvasara (Mukhapaka)</i>	Y.R.Samastamukharoga Chi. 1 Pg. no.306
12.	<i>Kavala with Taila prepared from Kaphanashaka Aushadi</i>	<i>Kaphaja Sarvasara (Mukhapaka)</i>	Y.R. Samastamukharoga chi. 3 pg no.307
13.	<i>After Sirabheda, Shirovirechana Kavala with Madhu, Gomutra, Goghrita, Ksheer and Sheetala Dravya</i>	<i>Mukhapaka</i>	Y.R. Mukhapaka chi. 1 pg no.307
14.	<i>Gandusha with Jatipatra Kwatha</i>	<i>Mukhapaka</i>	Y.R. Mukhapaka chi. 2 pg no.307
15.	<i>Patoladi Kwatha Kavala</i>	<i>Mukharoga</i>	Y.R. Mukhapaka chi. 9 pg no.307
16.	<i>Tila, Neelautapala, Ghrita Sharkara, Ksheer, & Lodhra - Gandusha</i> <i>Gandusha with Taila or Amlakanji</i>	<i>Mukhadagdha</i> <i>Mukhadagdha (with Tambulamadhya Sthita Churan)</i>	Y. R. Mukhapaka chi. 10 pg no.307 Y. R. Anyayoga pg no.308
17.	<i>Arimedadi Taila</i>	<i>Mukharuja, Pradushta Mansa, Chalita Danta, Kshiran Danta, Saushira, Dantaharsha, Dantavidradhi, krimidanta, Dantasafotana, Daurgandhya, Jihwataluoshtha Ruja</i>	Y.R. Samanya Chikitsa 1-5, Pg No. 302
18.	<i>Lakshadi Taila</i>	<i>Dantaroga</i>	Y.R. 1-4 pg no. 302
19.	<i>Kavala with Taila prepared from Vatanashaka Aushadhi</i>	<i>Dantaroga</i>	Y.R.Dantaroga Chi. 1 pg no. 301

Table no. 7: *Kavala and Gandusha in Mukha Roga mentioned in Chakradutta.*^[9]

Sr. no.	Drug and mode of administration	Indication	Reference
1.	<i>Kaphanashaka Kavala</i>	<i>Kaphaja Oshtha Roga</i>	C.D. 56(1/5) Pg no 325
2.	<i>Lodhradi gandusha</i>	<i>Saushira</i>	C.D. 56(2/10) pg no 326
3.	<i>Sukhoshana Sneha Kavala or Trivrita Taila Kavala or Bhadrardavyadi Kwatha Kavala</i> <i>Taila prepared with Vatanashaka Aushadhi – Kavala</i>	<i>Dantaharsha</i>	C.D. 56(2/25) pg. no. 328 C.D. 56(2/6) pg no. 326
4.	<i>Gandusha prepared from Madhu, Ghrita, Sharkara mixed with Kshirivriksha Kwatha</i>	<i>Dantaveshta</i>	C.D. 56(2/9) pg no. 326
5.	<i>Pipplayadi Kavala</i>	<i>Upkusha</i>	C.D.56(2/13) Pg no. 326
6.	<i>Nagarmotha & Sarshapa Kwatha Triphala Kwatha – Gandusha</i>	<i>Paridara</i>	C.D.56(2/1) pg no 325
7.	<i>After Swedana do Raktamokshana, Avapeedana Nasya then Vatanashaka Sneha – Gandusha or Brihatyadi Kwatha</i>	<i>Krimidanta(immovable)</i>	C.D.56(2/29) pg no. 328 C.D.56(2/30) pg no. 328
8.	<i>Katsareya Kwatha Gandusha Bakula Twaka Kwatha – Gandusha</i>	<i>Chaladanta</i>	C.D. 56(2/3) Pg no 325

			C.D. 56(2/7) pg no. 326
9.	<i>Makshikadi Kavala</i>	<i>Danta Shoola</i>	C.D.56(2/8) pg no. 326
10.	<i>Jatyadikwatha Gandusha</i>	<i>Danta Nadi</i>	C.D.56(2/22) pg no 327
11.	<i>Vachadi Kshaya Kavala</i>	<i>Jihwa Roga</i>	C.D.56(3/11) pg no 330
12.	<i>Sneha Kavala</i>	<i>Vataja Rohini</i>	C.D.56(4/4) Pg no. 331
13.	<i>Kavala with Draksha & Parushaka Kwatha</i>	<i>Pittaja Rohini</i>	C.D. 56(4/5) Pg no. 331
14.	<i>Kavala with Taila prepared from Shveta, Vidanga, Danti Kalka mixed with Saindhava Lavana</i>	<i>Kaphaja Rohini</i>	C.D. 56(4/6-7) Pg no. 331
15.	<i>Kavala with Taila prepared from Vatanashaka Aushadhi</i>	<i>Vataja Sarvasara (Mukhapaka)</i>	C.D. 56(4/25) Pg no. 333
16.	<i>Kaphanashaka gandusha</i>	<i>Kaphaja sarvasara (Mukhapaka)</i>	C.D.56(4/27) Pg no. 333
17.	<i>Jatipatradi Kwatha Gandusha</i> <i>Rasanjanadi Churan Kavala</i>	<i>Mukhapaka</i>	C.D. 56(4/29) Pg no. 333 C.D. 56(4/31) Pg no. 333
18.	<i>Patoladi Kwatha Kavala</i>	<i>Mukharoga</i>	C.D.56(4/36) Pg no. 334
19.	<i>Tiladi Gandusha</i>	<i>Mukhadaha</i>	C.D.56(4/38-39) Pg no. 334
20.	<i>Kavala with Nagarmotha, Kutha, Ela, Dhanyaka, Yashtimadhu& Elvalu Churan</i>	<i>Mukhadaurgandhya</i>	C.D. 56(4/40) Pg no. 334
21.	<i>Mahasehachara Taila</i>	<i>Dantadridata</i>	C.D.56(4/41-42) Pg no. 335
22.	<i>Irimedadya Taila</i>	<i>Danta Roga</i>	C.D. 56(4/40) Pg no. 335
23.	<i>Lakshaadyam Tailam</i>	<i>Mukha Roga</i>	C.D.56(4/48-51) Pg no. 335
24.	<i>Bakuladi Taila</i>	<i>Dantasthirta</i>	C.D.56(4/52-53) Pg no. 335

DISCUSSION

The present study highlights the profound therapeutic potential of *Kavala* and *Gandusha Yogas* in the management of *Mukharoga* (oral diseases), as described in classical Ayurvedic texts. These procedures, though simple, offer a remarkably holistic approach by combining mechanical cleansing, pharmacological action of medicated liquids, and stimulation of oropharyngeal reflexes. The use of medicated oils, decoctions, and herbal liquids in *Kavala* and *Gandusha* provides both local and systemic benefits. The *Snehana* and *Shodhana* actions helps to remove accumulated *doshic* impurities, reduce inflammation, and enhance mucosal resistance. This is especially relevant in conditions such as stomatitis, gingivitis, glossitis, halitosis, and mucosal dryness, which often have multifactorial etiologies. The mechanical swishing in *Kavala* improves salivary secretion, enhances local circulation, and removes debris and pathogens, thereby supporting oral hygiene. In

contrast, *Gandusha*, where the medicated liquid is held statically, exerts prolonged contact of the drug with oral tissues, making it particularly effective in conditions involving burning sensation, ulcerations, and pitta-dominant disorders. The difference in technique thus influences both the depth and intensity of therapeutic action. Furthermore, oil-based formulations show promising effects on periodontal health by inhibiting plaque formation and improving gingival scores, providing a contemporary validation to the classical practice of oil pulling. Their incorporation into daily *Dinacharya* may significantly reduce the burden of common oral disorders.

CONCLUSION

Kavala and *Gandusha Yogas* emerge as highly effective, safe, and accessible Ayurvedic interventions for managing various *Mukharogas*. Their combined mechanical, pharmacological, and therapeutic actions

help cleanse the oral cavity, reduce inflammation, promote healing, and enhance overall oral health. Supported by classical Ayurvedic principles and growing modern evidence, these practices offer a valuable integrative approach for both treatment and daily preventive care. Further well-designed clinical studies will help consolidate their role in contemporary oral healthcare.

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